

Thermal conductivity determination of an 18650 cylindrical lithium-ion cell based on thermal abuse transient responses using coupled finite difference method and Newton-Raphson algorithm with exact derivatives

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Methodology

Fundamental ‘unsteady’ state one dimensional cylindrical cell energy equation

In my previous report, in determining the thermal conductivity of a cylindrical cell, I utilized one dimensional (1D) steady-state energy equation in cylindrical coordinates to describe the problem. However, the cylindrical cell does not approach steady state during thermal runaway (TR) and the steady state assumption is no longer valid. As such, the unsteady 1D cylindrical energy equation should be used as a minimum, for determining the thermal conductivity of the cell.

Figure 1: 2D axisymmetric view of the 18650 cylindrical cell and 1D equivalent representation.

The strong form 1D axisymmetric energy equation is given as:

$$\kappa \left[\frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial r^2} \right] + \dot{q}_{el} = \rho C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} \quad 1$$

Subject to the following symmetry and Neumann boundary conditions at the external surface and axis of symmetry given as

$$\kappa_w \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=R_0} = -h(T - T_\infty) + \dot{q}_{surf,o}, \quad \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \Big|_{r=0} = 0 \quad 2$$

where T is the temperature in K , κ is the thermal conductivity in $W/m - K$, ρ is the density in kg/m^3 , C_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure in kg/m^3 , \dot{q}_{el} is the volumetric source specific heat rate in W/m^3 , h is the convective heat flux in $W/m^2 - K$ and T_∞ is the ambient temperature in K . The dimensions and material properties to be considered in this study are given in Table 1 below. Additionally, for the Neumann boundary condition, a value of $h = 7.17 W/m^2 - K$, and $T_\infty = T_{\infty,0} + 2 \text{ } ^\circ C/min$ was considered, where the reference temperature $T_{\infty,0} = 25 \text{ } ^\circ C$. It is assumed that in a typical thermal abuse simulation, the cell is heated with patch heaters attached to the surface of the battery and the surface temperature is measured with centrally spaced thermocouples attached to the cell surface. The heater power considered is $\dot{Q}_{surf,o} = 906W$ and the heater is activated for 110 s.

Table 1: Dimensions and average material properties of the 18650 cylindrical cell.

Dimension				Properties			
R_i	R_0	h_{jr}	t_{case}	ρ	C_p	κ_r	κ_{case}
[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[mm]	[kg/m ³]	[J/kg - K]	[W/m - K]	[W/m - K]
1.925	8.85	59.16	0.35	2055.2	1400	0.89724	24.5

Finite difference solution to the unsteady 1D energy equation

Unfortunately, explicit integral solutions for the temperature field to the above partial differential equation (PDE) even with the 1D simplification requires infinite series solutions which are mathematically rigorous especially when derivatives are required (as would be needed for an inverse analysis). A common practice to resolve the above problem is to discretize the equation using numerical approximation methods such as the finite difference (FD) technique. The FD discretization to Equation 1 has the form given as:

$$\kappa \left[\frac{1}{(i-1)\Delta r} \frac{[T_{i+1}^{k+1} - T_{i-1}^{k+1}]}{2\Delta r} + \frac{T_{i+1}^{k+1} - 2T_i^{k+1} + T_{i-1}^{k+1}}{\Delta r^2} \right] + \dot{q}_{el} - \rho C_p \frac{[T_i^{k+1} - T_i^k]}{\Delta t} = 0 \quad 3$$

The above equation can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa \Delta t (2i-3) T_{i-1}^{k+1} - 2(i-1) [2\kappa \Delta t + \Delta r^2 \rho C_p] T_i^{k+1} + \kappa \Delta t (2i-1) T_{i+1}^{k+1} \\ = -2(i-1) \Delta r^2 [\Delta t \dot{q}_{el} + \rho C_p T_i^k] \end{aligned} \quad 4$$

The FD constraint equations are likewise given as

$$-3T_i^{k+1} + 4T_{i+1}^{k+1} - T_{i+2}^{k+1} = 0, \quad i = 1 \quad 5$$

$$\kappa_w T_{i-2}^{k+1} - 4\kappa_w T_{i-1}^{k+1} + [3\kappa_w - 2h\Delta r] T_i^{k+1} = 2\Delta r [\dot{q}_{surf,o} - hT_\infty], \quad i = n_i \quad 6$$

The transient solution of the temperature field can be obtained by assembling the individual nodal equations into an algebraic system of equations of the form

$$\underline{\underline{A}} \cdot \underline{\underline{T}} = \underline{\underline{B}} \quad 7$$

Figure 2: Transient Temperature profiles of the (a) cell surface temperature (blue) and average cell temperature (red) from the forward F.D analysis and (b) input cell surface temperature (blue) and calculated thermal conductivity (red) from the inverse F.D/N.R analysis.

Utilizing transient data from actual T.R experiment

The TR excel data sheet, provides transient data for the cell current, $I_{cell}(t)$, the cell internal voltage, $\vartheta_{ocv}(t)$, the heater voltage, $\vartheta_{heater}(t)$, the ambient temperature, $T_{\infty}(t)$ and the temperature at the heater insert surface, $T_i(t)$. A constant heater current of $I_{heater} = 0.53A$ was used. The heat generated within the jelly roll, \dot{q}_{jr} given a volume V_{jr} , is calculated from the internal cell wattage \dot{Q}_{cell} due to current I_{cell} according to Eqn. 18.

$$\dot{Q}_{cell} = I_{cell}\vartheta_{ocv}, \quad \dot{q}_{jr} = \dot{Q}_{cell}/V_{jr} \quad 18$$

Likewise, the heater power \dot{Q}_{heater} is used to determine the heat flux through the surface of the insert at location r_i i.e., $\dot{q}_{s,i}$ according to Eqn. 19.

$$\dot{Q}_{heater} = I_{heater}\vartheta_{heater}, \quad \dot{q}_{surf,i} = \dot{Q}_{heater}/A_{surf,i} \quad 19$$

The profiles of the power generated within the cell, \dot{Q}_{cell} and heater, \dot{Q}_{heater} based on the TR data appears in Figure 3a. The cells internal power \dot{Q}_{cell} , is seen to be very small, $\sim 10\mu W$ order of magnitude and can be neglected. The only useful heater is that of the heater, \dot{Q}_{heater} (cf. Figure 3a). Transient profiles for temperature at the heater's surface T_i and the ambient temperature T_{∞} appear in Figure 3b. The battery heats up uniformly to about $T_i = 142.8^\circ C$ at the onset of thermal runaway at approximately $t_{TR,onset} = 1027s$, which is followed by a sudden jump in the temperature to about $T_i = 644.5^\circ C$ within the space of 18s due to the thermal runaway of the cell. During the TR event, additional heat is generated from the exothermic reactions within the cell that results in the rapid temperature rise of the cell which is not provided in the TR data. The TR data is thus only valid for predicting the thermal conductivity of the cell up to the TR trigger.

Figure 3: (a) Power generated with the $\dot{Q}_{cell} [W]$ and heater $\dot{Q}_{heater} [W]$ (b) Temperature at the heater surface, $T_i [^{\circ}C]$ and ambient temperature $T_{\infty} [^{\circ}C]$ transient profiles from thermal abuse test data.

The standard MoliCel 18650 dimensions and properties are used as in Table 1. To utilize the TR data, the applied B.C. on the cell would be modified. While the convective heat flux boundary condition at the cells external surface is retained, the constant heat flux at this surface is omitted due to the absence of external patch heaters, i.e. $\dot{q}_{surf,0} = 0$. Rather, an internal heat flux, $\dot{q}_{surf,i}$ is imposed at location R_i corresponding to the surface location of the heater insert, i.e.

$$\kappa_w \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R_i} = \dot{q}_{surf,i} \quad 20$$

Consequently, an additional system's equation at location $i = r$ is modified with Eqn. 21 below

$$\kappa_w [T_{i+1}^{k+1} - T_{i-1}^{k+1}] = 2\Delta r \dot{q}_{surf,i} \quad 21$$

i.e. the system matrix $\underline{\underline{A}}$, the field vector \underline{B} and consequently $\nabla \underline{\underline{A}}$ are modified such that

$$A_{r,r-1} = -\kappa_w, \quad A_{r,r} = 0, \quad A_{r,r+1} = \kappa_w, \quad B_r = 2\Delta r \dot{q}_{surf,i}, \quad \nabla A_{r,1-n} = 0 \quad 22$$

The residual R^- would in this case would depend on the known temperature $T_i(t)$ at the inner location (R_i), i.e. $R^- = T_2^- - T_i$. In the previous NR. solution technique, the system matrix, $\underline{\underline{A}}$ was partitioned into the 'known' - T_2 and 'unknown' - T_1 temperature degrees' of freedom (dofs), wherein the known temperature value, T_2 was the external surface temperature, T_0 corresponding to the last (n^{th}) data point of the temperature vector $T_n = T_0$. However, in the current analysis, T_2 corresponds to the heater surface temperature T_i , at an intermediate r^{th} location of the temperature vector $T_r = T_i$ (cf. Eqn. 23).

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{1,1} & \dots & A_{1,r-1} & A_{1,r} & A_{1,r+1} & \dots & A_{1,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{r-1,1} & \dots & A_{r-1,r-1} & \vdots & A_{r-1,r+1} & \dots & A_{r-1,n} \\ A_{r,1} & \dots & \dots & A_{r,r} & \dots & \dots & A_{r,n} \\ A_{r+1,1} & \dots & A_{r+1,r-1} & \vdots & A_{r+1,r+1} & \dots & A_{r+1,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{n,1} & \dots & A_{n,r-1} & A_{n,r} & A_{n,r+1} & \dots & A_{n,n} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T_1 \\ \vdots \\ T_{r-1} \\ T_r \\ T_{r+1} \\ \vdots \\ T_n \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ \vdots \\ B_{r-1} \\ B_r \\ B_{r+1} \\ \vdots \\ B_n \end{bmatrix} \quad 23$$

As such, reordering of the system matrix is required prior to partitioning to use the NR. solution technique of Eqns. 10-17 such that T_r is moved to T_n location and the pivot $A_{r,r}$ is moved to $A_{n,n}$. Basically, tensors

\underline{T} , \underline{B} , \underline{A} , and consequently $\nabla \underline{A}$ in Eqn. 23 are transformed to the form of Eqn. 24 through appropriate indexing operations.

$$\begin{bmatrix} A_{1,1} & \dots & A_{1,r-1} & A_{1,r+1} & \dots & A_{1,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{r-1,1} & \dots & A_{r-1,r-1} & A_{r-1,r+1} & \dots & A_{r-1,n} \\ A_{r+1,1} & \dots & A_{r+1,r-1} & A_{r+1,r+1} & \dots & A_{r+1,n} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ A_{n,1} & \dots & A_{n,r-1} & A_{n,r+1} & \dots & A_{n,n} \\ \hline A_{r,1} & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & A_{r,n} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} A_{1,r} \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ A_{n,r} \\ \hline A_{r,r} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T_1 \\ \vdots \\ T_{r-1} \\ T_{r+1} \\ \vdots \\ T_n \\ \hline T_r \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} B_1 \\ \vdots \\ B_{r-1} \\ B_{r+1} \\ \vdots \\ B_n \\ \hline B_r \end{bmatrix} \quad 24$$

The results from the revised inverse analysis using the TR data are presented in the following section. Figure 4a shows 1D transient temperature ramp profiles of the jelly roll through time. The jelly roll temperature T_{jr} is seen to increase monotonically over time. From the axisymmetric axis to the heater surface at location at location R_i , the instantaneous temperature profile is fairly constant, however beyond R_i , the temperature drops gradually at a steady rate to some lower value at R_0 . Figure 4b also shows that the average jelly roll temperature, \bar{T}_{jr} increases monotonically over time. The transient thermal conductivity profile, κ_{jr} from the NR calculation, shows an initial ramp up about $\kappa_{jr} = 4.2 \text{ W/m-K}$ at roughly $t = 127 \text{ s}$ followed by an average decline to about $\kappa_{jr} = 1.53 \text{ W/m-K}$ at approximately $t = 852 \text{ s}$. Beyond this point, the κ_{jr} value is unstable and continues to rise probably in response to TR event. The computed κ_{jr} values are within the ballpark of estimated values used in literature (see for instance, Ref. 1, $\kappa_{jr} = 3.4 \text{ W/m-K}$).

Figure 4: (a) 1D transient temperature profiles of the jelly roll (b) average jelly-roll transient temperature profile, \bar{T}_{jr} (blue) and calculated thermal conductivity transient profile κ_{jr} (red).

Figure 5 shows the plot of the thermal conductivity transient profile κ_{jr} against the average jelly-roll transient temperature profile, \bar{T}_{jr} . Linear regression fit using data within the useful range of $33.5^\circ\text{C} \leq \bar{T}_{jr} \leq 93.5^\circ\text{C}$ shows that the jelly rolls thermal conductivity decreases with increasing temperature. This directly follows conclusion from literature [1]. The κ_{jr} value above has been calculated assuming a cartridge heater 300 series stainless steel sheath wall conductivity of $\kappa_w = 14.5 \text{ W/m-K}$ which falls within typical range found in literature [3]. It is worth noting that the computed κ_{jr} is dependent on the κ_w and could fall within range as low as $0.55 \leq \kappa_{jr} \leq 1.64 \text{ W/m-K}$ with a κ_w value of $\kappa_w = 5.5 \text{ W/m-K}$. The foregoing

discussion shows that the thermal conductivity of a cylindrical cell could be approximated using data derived from TR experiment.

Figure 5: Calculated thermal conductivity transient profile κ_{jr} versus the average jelly-roll transient temperature profile, \bar{T}_{jr} (red line) and linear regression fit of the $\kappa_{jr} - \bar{T}_{jr}$ data (black line).

Conclusion

In conclusion, a coupled numerical finite difference scheme and Newton Raphson algorithm using exact derivatives has been utilized to calculate the thermal conductivity of an 18650 lithium-ion cylindrical cell based on transient responses from a typical thermal abuse data and assuming unsteady one-dimensional axisymmetric energy balance governing equation. The study shows that the coupled numerical approach can accurately backtrack the cell's thermal conductivity prior to the thermal runaway event.

References

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